

STUDIES ON THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT. PART III

BY A. B. SEN AND V. S. MISRA

Several *o*-hydroxy-ketones have been prepared by the Fries rearrangement of esters of $\alpha\beta$ -nonenoic acid.

The Fries rearrangement of esters of several unsaturated aliphatic acids has already been described in the first two parts of this series (Sen and Misra, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 393; 1949, 26, 149). In all the three cases studied so far, only *o*-hydroxy-ketones were obtained. In the present paper this reaction has been extended to four esters of $\alpha\beta$ -nonenoic acid, viz., phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresyl, which on treatment with anhydrous aluminium chloride have been found to rearrange mainly into *o*-hydroxy-ketones. The ketones have been characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

$\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic acid was prepared by the method described by Harding and Weizmann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 301). Malonic acid (57 g.) was dissolved in dry pyridine (93 c.c.) and to the ice-cooled mixture was gradually added *n*-heptaldehyde (57 g.). The mixture was allowed to stand at the room temperature (28°-32°) for 60 hours with frequent shaking, and finally heated on a water-bath for 6 hours. On acidification with 25% hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.), the $\alpha\beta$ -nonenoic acid separated out as an oil. It was taken up in benzene, washed with water, dried and distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 147°/7mm. (Harding and Weizmann, *loc. cit.* report b.p. 144°/13mm.), yield 65% of theory.

Chloride of $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic Acid.— $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic acid (20 g.) and thionyl chloride (28 g.) were refluxed together for 4 hours on a water-bath. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed and the chloride distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 104°/10mm. (Harding, *loc. cit.* reports b.p. 144°/90mm.).

Phenyl Ester of $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic Acid.—To phenol (4.8 g.), taken in a round bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a dropping funnel, was gradually added $\alpha\beta$ -nonenoyl chloride (9 g.) and the mixture was heated on a water-bath till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. On cooling and addition of cold water, the ester separated out as an oil which was then extracted with ether, washed with water, 1% caustic soda and then again with water. The ethereal solution was dehydrated over anhydrous calcium chloride and the ether removed. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure when the ester was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. 151°-152°/1mm., yield 10 g. (Found: C, 77.41; H, 8.43. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77.58; H, 8.62 per cent).

**o*-Cresyl Ester of $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic Acid.*— $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoyl chloride (10 g.) was heated with freshly distilled *o*-cresol (6 g.) and the ester obtained in the usual manner, b.p. 176°/4mm., yield 10.5 g. (Found: C, 77.91; H, 8.81. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94 per cent).

m-Cresyl Ester of $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic Acid.—To *m*-cresol (6 g.) was added $\alpha\beta$ -nonenoyl chloride (10 g.) and the ester isolated as usual, b.p. 167°/4mm., yield 9.5 g. (Found : C, 77.88 ; H, 8.65. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04 ; H, 8.94 per cent).

p-Cresyl Ester of $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic Acid.—The acid chloride (9 g.) was added to *p*-cresol (5.6 g.) and the ester isolated in the usual manner, b.p. 181°/3mm., yield 9 g. (Found : C, 77.76 ; H, 9.05. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04 ; H, 8.94 per cent).

Fries Rearrangement of the Phenyl Ester of $\alpha\beta$ -Nonenoic Acid.—The ester (8 g.) was gradually added to finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.8 g.) taken in a 250 c.c. round bottom flask, fitted with an upright condenser and a dropping funnel. The mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 hours and to the bluish red puffy mass obtained, dilute hydrochloric acid was added. A bluish oil separated out after some time, which was taken up in ether and washed successively with water, 1% sodium carbonate solution and finally with water. The ethereal extract was dehydrated over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the ether the residue was distilled under reduced pressure when a light blue oil was obtained at 120°/2mm., yield 4.4 g. It conformed to the characteristic tests of *o*-hydroxyketones (Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) and was identified as 1-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-non-2-ene-1-one. (Found : C, 77.32 ; H, 8.86. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77.58 ; H, 8.62 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained in the usual manner as red crystals, m.p. 201° (Found : N, 13.78. $C_{21}H_{24}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.59 per cent).

1-(2'-Hydroxy-3'-methylphenyl)-non-2-ene-1-one.—The above ketone was obtained by heating *o*-cresyl ester of $\alpha\beta$ -nonenoic acid (8 g.) with anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.5 g.) and the *o*-hydroxy-ketone isolated as in the preceding case, b.p. 139°/3mm., yield 4.2 g. (Found : C, 78.26 ; H, 8.72. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04 ; H, 8.94 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, obtained in the usual manner, melted at 217-18°. (Found : N, 12.84. $C_{22}H_{26}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.14 per cent).

1-(2'-Hydroxy-4'-methylphenyl)-non-2-ene-1-one.—The *m*-cresyl ester (9 g.) was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (7.2 g.) and the above ketone was obtained as a greenish oil, b.p. 142°/4mm., yield 5 g. (Found : C, 78.36 ; H, 9.22. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04, H, 8.94 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as before, m.p. 221°. (Found : N, 12.79. $C_{22}H_{26}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.14 per cent).

1-(2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylphenyl)-non-2-ene-1-one.—*p*-Cresyl ester (8 g.) on heating with anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.5 g.) gave exclusively the above ketone, b.p. 132°/4mm., yield 4.9 g. (Found : C, 77.59 ; H, 9.42. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04 ; H, 8.94 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained as described previously, m.p. 209°. (Found : N, 13.33. $C_{22}H_{26}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.14 per cent).